

MNDO Study of Reaction Paths : Hydroboration of Organic Nitriles*

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MNDO molecular orbital calculations are reported for the reaction of BH_3 with HCN. The results indicate that the reaction proceeds exothermally via an intermediate linear complex, with an activation barrier of 21.3 kcal/mol. In the gas phase, the reaction is shown to proceed in two stages: the formation of the linear complex and its rearrangement to the product via intramolecular hydrogen migration. The adduct has a donor-acceptor type of bond between nitrogen and boron. The possibility of an alternative mechanism, involving the direct attack of the carbon-nitrogen π -bond by borane, resulting in a π -complex having a three-center two-electron bond, as in the case of acetylene (which has a homopolar triple bond), has been eliminated. Charge transfer effects have also been discussed.

RECENTLY, the hydroboration reaction has attracted the interest of a large number of theoretical chemists¹⁻⁶. Most of these studies were, however, confined to the hydroboration reactions of alkenes and alkynes. Similar reactions are also shown by heteropolar double and triple bonds^{7,8}. The hydroboration of organic nitriles is of particular importance since it provides a convenient route to the synthesis of amines. In view of this, we decided to carry out a study of this reaction to determine the nature of the stationary points on the reaction surface, and the activation energy barrier for the reaction.

Method of calculation: The MNDO method with the usual parameters^{9,10} was used for all the molecular orbital calculations reported here. Equilibrium geometries were optimized using the Davidson-Fletcher-Powell method¹¹.

The transition state geometry was located by the energy minimization method, using the length of the forming C-H bond as the reaction coordinate. Rothman and Lohr¹² have pointed out that the maxima obtained on such reaction surfaces are saddle points, provided the reaction pathway is continuous in that region. According to these authors¹² the force constant matrix at such points has one, and only one, negative eigen value.

Results and Discussion

The product of the hydroboration of nitriles contains the boron atom bonded to the nitrogen.

In the present work, we have studied the energy profile for this reaction. For the sake of simplicity we have studied only the case for $R=H$.

A CNDO/2 study of this reaction by Datta *et al*¹³ indicated that it proceeds through a transition state having a three-center bond. In the course of our present calculations, we found that a three-center geometry is neither a transition state, nor an intermediate. There is no three-center stationary point on the reaction surface. In fact, diborane is a Lewis acid which functions best as a reducing agent in attacking groups at positions of high electron density, such as the nitrogen atom of the nitrile group, which is relatively basic. This nitrogen is known to add to boron trifluoride to form addition compounds of moderate stability¹³. Presumably, the rapid reduction of nitriles by diborane involves an initial attack of this reagent on this relatively basic position, as originally suggested by Brown and Subba Rao¹⁴. We first identified the product of the reaction. Optimization of the geometry, keeping the BH_2 group in the same plane as the $H \setminus C-N$ group, gives a structure having a heat of formation of 19.2 kcal/mol and a CNB angle of 124.4°. However, if the BH_2 group is allowed to rotate about the B-N bond, the geometry optimizes to a structure having the BH_2 group normal to the plane of the CH_2 group and a heat of formation of 5.2 kcal/mol. Surprisingly, the CNB bonds also become linear. This structure (P), is shown in Fig. 1.

The reaction profile is shown in Fig. 2. There are two transition states and one intermediate along the reaction path. The linear adduct is initially formed as a stable intermediate. The activation energy required for its formation is 3.8 kcal/mol. The optimized geometries of the transition state (T1) and the adduct (A) are shown in Fig. 1. The adduct (A) is more stable than the reactants by 19.8 kcal/mol. The second step in the reaction is the

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Fig. 1. Optimized geometries (in angstroms and degrees) of the transition state (T1) for the formation of adduct, the adduct (A), the transition state (T2) for the formation of product and the product (P).

Fig. 2. The energy profile (kcal/mol) for the reaction of HCN with BH_3 .

rearrangement of the adduct to the product. This requires an activation energy of 41.1 kcal/mol. This is thus the rate-determining step. The transition state (T2), shown in Fig. 1, has a four-center-like structure.

The overall activation energy for the reaction is thus 21.3 kcal/mol. Although the experimental gas phase value for the activation energy is not available, our value seems reasonable. Brown and Korytnyk^{1,5} had observed that, in solution, nitriles are less reactive than olefins towards hydroboration. The MNDO calculated² barrier for hydroboration of ethylene is 7.6 kcal/mol. The enthalpy of hydroboration of HCN is found to be -41.5 kcal/mol and the reaction is exothermic. On going from the reactant to the product, the B-N bond distance at first decreases until the linear adduct is formed. It then increases to a value of about 1.7 Å, after which it decreases to its value of 1.35 Å for the product. Similarly, the CNB angle remains constant at 180° until the linear adduct is formed, after which it decreases to a value of 76.4° near the second transition state, T2. The CNB bond angle then increases, until it becomes linear in the product.

Charge transfer effects : It is also pertinent to examine the charge transfer effects accompanying the above-mentioned reaction. In Table 1, we have given the charges on various atoms in the reactants (R), at the transition state (T1) for the formation of adduct, at the adduct (A), at the transition state (T2) for the formation of product, and at the product (P). There is a very negligible change in the charges on going from the reactants to T1. At T1, only 0.03 units of electronic charge is transferred from the HCN moiety to the BH_3

TABLE 1 - CHARGES ON VARIOUS ATOMS IN THE STATIONARY POINTS ON THE REACTION SURFACE (SEE FIG. 2)

Atom ^a	Charge (Q)				
	R	T1	A	T2	P
H ₁	0.19	0.20	0.23	0.17	0.03
C	-0.09	-0.05	0.05	0.14	0.23
N	-0.10	-0.12	0.10	-0.08	-0.33
B	0.24	0.21	-0.17	-0.17	0.06
H ₂	-0.08	-0.08	-0.07	-0.06	0.03
H _{3,4}	-0.08	-0.08	-0.07	0.00	-0.01

^a See Fig. 1 for numbering of hydrogens.

moiety. Therefore, it resembles the reactants more closely than the adduct (A). As the reaction proceeds from T1 to A, there is a negligible effect on the hydrogens, but the carbon, nitrogen and boron atoms reverse their charges. In the adduct, 0.38 units of charge is transferred from the HCN moiety to the BH_3 moiety. Of this, 0.20 units of charge come from the nitrogen, while the carbon atom donates about 0.14 units of charge to the boron. In T2, the amount of transfer reduces to 0.23 units. This is mainly due to back donation of charge to the nitrogen and the hydrogen of the HCN moiety. In the product, the nitrogen atom becomes more negatively charged, while the carbon becomes more positively charged. The boron atom again becomes positively charged. As the reaction proceeds from T2 to P, there is transfer of charge from boron to nitrogen.

Conclusions : Our calculations have indicated that the hydroboration of hydrogen cyanide proceeds in two stages. The first is the formation of the linear adduct and the second is its rearrangement to the product. The latter is the rate-determining step. The reaction is exothermic and has a large negative enthalpy. The possibility of the reaction taking place via a three-center intermediate or transition state, as suggested by Datta *et al*⁵, is completely ruled out. The intermediate complex is found to be linear and the transition state has a four-center-like structure. The intermediate complex is much more stable than the reactants. The overall mechanism proposed from the results of the present theoretical study is in agreement with that originally suggested by Brown and Subba Rao^{1,4}.

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